

Foo

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November 16, 2024

1 Introduction

It is well known that in order to compute the sum of the first N integers, one simply calculates the value of $((N)N + 1)/2$. For an arbitrary base B and an equation of the form

$$Q_{;k(B)} = \sum_{q=p}^{kB} q \quad (1.1)$$

For

$$p = (k - 1)B + 1$$

we can calculate the value of x by

$$x = \sum_{q=1}^{kB} q - \sum_{q'=p'}^{kB} q' \quad (1.2)$$

where

$$p' = (k - 2)B + 1$$

This gives us

$$\sum_{q=p}^{kB} q = \left((kB)(kB + 1) \right) / 2 - \left(((k - 1)B)((k - 1)B + 1) \right) / 2 \quad (1.3)$$

Let us denote the expression $1 + 2 + \dots + B$ by $1\dots B = \sigma_1$; we will further rewrite $(B + 1)\dots(2B)$ by σ_2 , etc., so that we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_k &= \left((k - 1)B + 1 \right) \dots kB \\ &= \sum_p^{kB} \\ &= Q_{;k(B)} \end{aligned} \quad (1.4)$$

where, explicitly, σ_k is called the *natural block* of rank k , and represents a formal sum over the interval $[(k - 1)B + 1, kB]$ of natural numbers.

If $B = 10$, for $B \leq kB \leq B^2$ (or, equivalently, for $1 \leq k \leq B$), we have the relation:

$$\sigma_k = (k - 1)B^2 + \sigma_1 \quad (1.5)$$

It follows that

$$\sigma_{k+a} - \sigma_1 = kB^2 + aB^2 - B^2$$

Setting $a = -1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{k-1} - \sigma_1 &= kB^2 - 2B^2 \\ &= (k - 2)B^2 \end{aligned} \quad (1.6)$$

If we set $k = 0$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{-1} - \sigma_1 &= -2B^2 \\ &= 2(iB)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (1.7)$$

If we again choose 10 as our base, we can do the following standard arithmetic:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{-1} &= 2(10i)^2 + \sigma_1 \\ &= 2 \cdot (10^2 \cdot -1) + 55 \\ &= -145 \end{aligned}$$

However, using formula (1.4), this is rewritten as:

$$\sigma_{-1} = \left(-1 - 1(11) \right) \dots - 10$$

which gives us -208 , which is a contradiction. This shows that the pattern breaks for $k < 0$.

Further, the pattern does not work for $k = 0$, as we get $0 + \sigma_1 \neq \left(-11 \right) \dots 0$.

A Calculations

B B=10

Only the first few terms are explicitly calculated. The rest follows from induction.

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{q=1}^{10} q & \\ &= (10(11))/2 \\ &= 55 \\ &= \sigma_1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{q=11}^{20} q & \\ &= (20(21))/2 - \sigma_1 \\ &= 155 \\ &= 55 + 10^2 \\ &= \sigma_1 + B^2 \\ &= \sigma_2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{q=21}^{30} q & \\ &= (30(31))/2 - (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) \\ &= 255 \\ &= 2B^2 + \sigma_1 \\ &= \sigma_3\end{aligned}$$